

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 3.6

LandSense Engagement Platform II

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Short Description:
<p>This report is part two of the deliverable LandSense Engagement Platform. Part one was delivered as D3.3 in February 2018.</p> <p>As such, this document provides a summary of the current state of the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP) focusing on the updates and improvements since publication of D3.3. Descriptions of the core services such as the LandSense Authorization Server, fundamental concepts like the LandSense Federation, and other services are available from D3.3.</p> <p>The public demonstrator of the LEP is accessible via https://www.landsense.eu/</p>
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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
AS	Authorization Server
CO	Citizen Observatory
CPU	Central Processing Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EO	Earth Observation
LEP	LandSense Engagement Platform
LULC	Land Use/Land Cover
LTS	Long Term Support
QA	Quality Assurance
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine

Executive Summary

The LandSense Engagement Platform brings together solutions that contribute to the transfer, assessment, valuation, uptake and exploitation of citizens' contributions, Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) data and related results of the LandSense project. The platform offers a common web portal to collaborative data collection and mapping functionalities allowing citizens and stakeholders to collect, view, analyse and share data from different campaigns.

In addition, the LandSense Engagement Platform exposes various services that are useful to developers and innovators dealing with citizen science and LULC. The platform is accessible to anyone, but some features are only available to logged-in users. To facilitate the uptake of the platform, login is possible using several social media accounts, LandSense partners' accounts and academic institutions participating in eduGAIN.

In particular, the connection to eduGAIN offers the collaboration of citizens with research organizations like universities on a global scale.

The LandSense Engagement Platform is now the default landing page for the LandSense project:

<https://www.landsense.eu/>.

1 Introduction to LandSense

The Earth Observation (EO) data economy is moving towards becoming a highly competitive market segment. Solution providers are reliant on high-quality data as they need to deliver contextually appropriate EO-based value-added products and services. Currently within the EU's EO monitoring framework, there is a need for low-cost methods for acquiring high quality in-situ data to create accurate and well-validated environmental monitoring products. Timely acquisition and processing of high-quality *in-situ* data plays a critical role in ensuring that EO data and resultant EO-based products are properly calibrated and validated. To help address this need, LandSense has built a citizen observatory to link remote sensing data with modern participatory data collection methods that involve citizen scientists for improved environmental monitoring. The LandSense Citizen Observatory (CO) is fostered through innovative and novel EO mobile applications, allowing citizens to not only play a key role in LULC monitoring, but also to be directly involved in the co-creation of such solutions.

A series of LandSense tools and services accessible via the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP) have being demonstrated across a series of campaigns to illustrate the power and flexibility of the LandSense CO to tackle different environmental monitoring issues.

- The **Urban Landscape Dynamics** theme focuses on engaging citizens via mobile applications to discover land change in urban and peri-urban areas. Pilot cases got implemented in Amsterdam, Toulouse, Vienna and Heidelberg to engage citizens in monitoring their local environment.
- The **Agriculture Land Use** theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added services to European farmers and public authorities in the agricultural sector. Demonstration cases were run in Serbia.
- The **Forest & Habitat Monitoring** theme triggers volunteer networks for in-situ data collection to help monitor protected areas within BirdLife International Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas and Key Biodiversity Areas through networks in Spain and Indonesia. Demonstration is ongoing.

This document provides an overview of the key components and functionality of the LandSense Engagement Platform by focusing on the updates since version one (D3.3) of this document.

2 The LandSense Engagement Platform

An important part of the LandSense Citizen Observatory is the LandSense Engagement Platform (Figure 1), a service platform comprised of EO-based solutions that contribute to the transfer, assessment, valuation, uptake and exploitation of LULC data and related results. The platform offers collaborative mapping functionalities to allow citizens to view, analyse and share data collected from different campaigns and create their own maps. In addition, citizens can participate in on-going LandSense campaigns using their own devices (e.g. mobile phones and tablets), through interactive reporting and gaming applications, as well as adding their own campaigns.

This interaction is achieved by bringing together and extending various key pieces of technology like: Geo-Wiki, LACO-Wiki, Geopedia, a number of mobile applications and novel services. The LandSense Engagement Platform, as described in this document provides the technical and legal basis to demonstrate the LandSense objective.

The LandSense Engagement Platform can be accessed via <https://www.landsense.eu/>.

Figure 1: Building blocks of the LandSense Engagement Platform

2.1 LandSense Authorization Server

The LandSense Authorization Server (AS) is part of the LEP that acts as a broker of user authentication and personal information between the Identity Providers of the LandSense Federation and the operators of registered applications and services. Each operator of registered applications and/or services can obtain a specific amount of personal information, individual for each application and service that they register.

The AS controls the provision of the collected personal information from users to operators' applications based on scopes. The amount of personal information that an operator can fetch is based on the scope(s) the application was registered with. Which scopes exist and which user attributes are linked with a scope can be determined from the Privacy Statement.

The collection, storage and processing of personal information is compliant with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The legal text regarding GDPR compliance can be obtained via the page <https://as.landsense.eu/PrivacyStatement>.

The LandSense Authorization Server is available at <https://as.landsense.eu>.

2.1.1 Upgrades and new functionality

Major improvements and new functions have been implemented since the first deployment as described in *D3.3: LandSense Engagement Platform I*. As a core service, the AS must be available as close to 100% as possible and scalable in terms of performance to guarantee a seamless support for all other applications and services of the LEP. To achieve the sustainability goal for the AS, a major redesign and implementation was done since the last deployment. Under the high-level requirement "availability, scalability and cloud-readiness", a modular design was created and implemented in the PHP programming language. In addition to the core redesign, the current version of the AS has built-in multi-lingual support for German, English, French, Greek and Spanish.

To demonstrate the cloud-readiness and in particular the provider independence of the software, the Authorization Server was deployed with DigitalOcean (<https://www.digitalocean.com>), Google GKE (<https://console.cloud.google.com/>), Amazon AKE (<https://console.aws.amazon.com>) and Azure (<https://portal.azure.com/>) leveraging Docker and Kubernetes as well as traditional cloud provider Hetzner (<https://www.hetzner.de>).

The combination of these modern technologies for software deployment control, comprised with git versioning control via Github and a test framework guarantees to maintain a high Technology Readiness Level (TRL). The current deployment is considered EU TRL¹.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level: "System prototype demonstration in operational environment"

This is the summary of the improvements and new features now available:

- Support for Proof Key for Code Exchange by OAuth Public Clients (RFC 7636) that ensures secure deployment of native apps like - mobile applications - as described in RFC 8252 (OAuth 2.0 for Native Apps). This exposes new parameter to the <https://as.landsense.eu/oauth/authorize> and <https://as.landsense.eu/oauth/token> endpoints.
- Support for OAuth 2.0 Dynamic Client Registration Protocol (RFC 7591) that supports an application to register dynamically without any user interaction (<https://as.landsense.eu/oauth/register>). In addition to the already existing manual registration option, this functionality is important to support mass deployment of applications like desktop applications. One prominent example is a QGIS plugin that allows to fetch data from services protected by OAuth2. (Note: LEP services are protected by OAuth2).
- API description in OpenAPI (<https://as.landsense.eu/api>) to engage developers when developing applications and services that interconnect with the Authorization Server.
- Multi-lingual support that can be easily extended to other languages including new page design based on Bootstrap CSS and JS.
- Support for cloud-based deployment based on Docker images and Kubernetes.
- Test framework to ensure appropriate functioning of the OAuth2 and OpenID Connect as well as the SAML2 federation support.
- Logging of personal information processing and download of the processing history in CSV or JSON format (<https://as.landsense.eu/saml/sessioninfo>). The personal data processing history is stored in encrypted form.

2.2 Upgrades of LandSense Core Services

The LandSense Engagement Platform building blocks are several core services, primarily supporting LandSense campaigns. This chapter shortly describes updates of said services since the Deliverable 3.3, which demonstrated the first version of the LEP.

2.2.1 Development support

The underlying component of the LandSense Federation is the Authorization Server (Figure 2). It is also the backbone of the LEP and its services. In order to facilitate the uptake of the LEP and its services and help developers either use the services or even bring their services onboard, the documentation of the AS has been described with the use of OpenAPI (Figure 3 and 4). The documentation is available at <https://as.landsense.eu/api> and describes all the programmatic calls necessary to interact with the federation.

Figure 2: LandSense Authorization Server

Figure 3: Authorisation service OpenAPI description, accessed 2020.02.20

Token Management		Get or revoke access and refresh tokens.	▼
GET	/oauth/authorize	The authorization endpoint for the 'authorization_code' workflow.	
POST	/oauth/token	Request a new access token.	🔒
POST	/oauth/tokenrevoke	Revoke a refresh token or an access token.	🔒
GET	/oauth/logout	Logout based on 'code', 'access_token' or 'refresh_token'.	
Introspection		Get information about access and refresh tokens.	▼
POST	/oauth/tokeninfo	Introspect a refresh token or an access token.	🔒
Claims		Get user claims	▼
GET	/openid/userinfo	Obtain user claims as defined in OpenID Connect.	🔒
POST	/openid/userinfo	Obtain user claims as defined in OpenID Connect.	🔒
Application Management		Register applications	▼
POST	/oauth/register	Register application with software statement.	

Figure 4: Access points descriptions that are needed for the OpenID Connect workflows give developers needed information to interact with LandSense Federation.

Automatic registration of applications into the authorisation server follows the Dynamic Client Registration Protocol (RFC 7591) and is particularly interesting for mass deployment of applications like desktop applications. The automatic registration endpoint is also described in the OpenAPI documentation under Application Management and is accessible at

<https://as.landsense.eu/api/#/Application%20Management/oauth2Register>.

The LandSense Authorization Server (AS) acts as a GDPR compliant broker between the personal information received after a user's login and registered applications based on user approval. In order to honour GDPR data minimisation, the AS requests from the Identity Provider (IdP) at login only that amount of personal information, as it is required by a registered application. This amount (and which attributes in detail) is controlled by the registration / login level. The AS provides five levels of which the first two do not enable an application to obtain personal information: **AUTH, CRYPTO, PROFILE, EMAIL, PROFILE+EMAIL**. To make this part clear to both developers and general public, users can use the Incremental Login OpenId Connection application, accessible at <https://landsense.eu/Project/IncrementalLogin> and check first-hand what kind of (personal) information is passed onwards based on the scope (Figure 5). Short descriptions of different scopes are also given, as can be seen in the screenshots below.

At the other end of the spectrum, logins with login level profile (and above) show which personal information from the Identity provider is being passed on to the registered application, but user has to give consent to it (Figure 7-9).

GDPR
Name: Joe

Login level: PROFILE

Any application that is registered with this level will be able to receive personal information as defined in the OpenID Connect specification for the scope profile (provide URL) after the user has given their approval. Any application operating on this level must be fully GDPR compliant, which means that the registration process requires to provide a URL to the privacy statement of the application. This privacy statement defines which personal information is requested, for which purpose and which operators will be able to also process the personal information. These are LandSense services that are used by the application. After login with Level PROFILE you will see the crypto name plus all available personal information that fall into the scope profile. Please note that you may only see a subset which means that the AS has not received more information.

LOGIN

Figure 7: Login level profile falls under the GDPR as it exposes personal information.

Hello Matej Batič
Do you authorize the Application

GDPR
Name: Joe

LEP incremental login PROFILE
operated by Sinergise located in Slovenia

to access the following personal data collected for the current session?

Last name: Batič
Given name: Matej
Preferred username: Matej Batič

The operator of this application has its seat inside the EU/EAA. Therefore, the operator of this application is contractually bound to comply with the EU [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#).

I hereby explicitly consent that the Authorization Server - this service - forwards the personal data in the scope determined by the operator of the application and in accordance with the [Privacy Statement](#) to the operator of this application.

Yes

Figure 8: The AS is strict about me giving consent that my personal information can be passed on to the registered application.

2.2.2 Change Detector Service

Several variations of change detector services have been developed within LandSense, with the primary aim of supporting support pilots across three themes (urban, agriculture and forest habitat monitoring). They are demonstrated on LEP (<https://www.landsense.eu/Innovate>), as can be seen in Figure 10.

The services are computationally intensive, and have been optimized for the LandSense pilots. As such, only the deforestation detection could be potentially run anywhere in the world. Nevertheless, to avoid abuse, the change detection services are not exposed directly to possible users.

Figure 10: The three change detection services, demonstrated on the LEP.

2.2.3 Quality Assurance and Control Service

The Quality Assurance and Control service is one of the main tools and services within the LandSense Federation. The service is being used within several LandSense demonstration pilots for both assessing the quality of citizen-based observations, as well as assuring the compliance with the GDPR for data dissemination. The service has been described in detail in *deliverable D3.5: Integration of quality assurance & control service I*.

To help developers, both the description of the endpoints as well as coding examples for the REST interfaces are available at <https://qatest.geopedia.world/wps-rest/swagger/index.html#/>. The quality assurance and control tests are grouped in several topics (Figure 11), ranging from spatial tests, thematic and positional accuracies to privacy and some tests developed and used specifically in some pilots.

To complement the online documentation, which is primarily meant for developers, we have implemented demonstration of three QA tests directly on LEP with simpler user interfaces, directed for the general public. The three tests implemented are

- Detection of polygon overlap
- Face detection and blurring
- Check image sharpness (detect blur)

The demos are available to logged in users at <https://landsense.eu/Innovate/QAS>.

Descriptions about how QA test have been used in LandSense pilots are also showcased on LEP at https://landsense.eu/Innovate/QA_data.

Figure 11: OpenAPI documentation of the Quality Assurance and Control service, showing two of the several topics.

2.2.4 Licensing Ontology

The Licensing Ontology tool (Figure 12) that helps users and developers pick the correct and appropriate licences for their data, has remained the same since the D3.3 - LandSense Engagement Platform I. It is accessible at <https://landsense.eu/Innovate/LicensingOntology>, and shown in the figure below.

License Features

Your choices on this panel will update the other panels on this page.

Allow unrestricted use of your work?

- Yes
- No

Allow adaptations of your work to be shared?

- Yes
- No
- Yes, as long as others share alike

Allow commercial uses of your work?

- Yes
- No

Selected License

Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0 International

Figure 12: By defining the license features, the licensing ontology tool outputs the appropriate license.

2.3 LandSense Campaigns

The explore section of the LandSense Engagement Platform allows the users to discover and directly contribute to ongoing LandSense campaigns <https://www.landsense.eu/Explore> (Figure 13). Each figure takes users to a specific campaign, providing overview information, web/mobile applications to contribute, descriptions and visualizations of data collected, and links to download data.

Map It!

Land use and land cover mapping in the Occitanie Region of France with the Paysages app

Integrate It!

OpenStreetMap, satellite imagery and machine learning to improve land cover and land use maps

CityOases

Find the perfect places to spend the day and share them with the City Oases App!

Feel It!

Crowdsourcing perceptions of urban green space quality

Acting For Nature!

Reporting threats to biodiversity and habitat changes in Spain

Build, Measure And Learn!

Assessing crop health with the CropSupport app

Figure 13: LandSense campaigns exposed on LEP.

2.4 LEP Integration with external services

Among the collection of LandSense campaigns, applications, tools and services, the LEP also integrates access to external services developed in other H2020 projects.

2.4.1 Geospatial User Feedback System

The Geospatial User Feedback System has been developed under the H2020 project NextGEOSS (grant agreement 730329) and can be accessed from LandSense Engagement Platform by visiting this link: <https://www.landsense.eu/Innovate/GUFService>.

Figure 14: The Geospatial User Feedback System.

2.4.2 SCENT Harmonization Platform

The SCENT Harmonization Platform has been developed under the H2020 SCENT project (grant agreement 688930) and can be accessed from LandSense Engagement Platform by visiting this link: <https://www.landsense.eu/Innovate>.

Figure 15: The SCENT Harmonization Platform.

3 Conclusions

The LEP is a living platform where new concepts and technical solutions are continually developed to address the challenges of managing federated users and distributed services. It addresses both citizen scientists, giving them tools to contribute to running campaigns, developers who would like to integrate LandSense services into their tools, as well as stakeholders and policy makers who would like to see, understand and use the outputs of the campaigns.

The LEP can also be accessed by researchers to obtain data for research. They can simply login via eduGAIN and their organizational account.

The platform is available at <https://www.landsense.eu/>.

4 References

The document labelled LandSense D3.3 - LandSense Engagement Platform I - can be downloaded from the Zenodo repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3670183>